

FINANCIAL PRODUCTIVITY; AN EVIDENCE-BASED REVIEW OF MANPOWER ANALYTICS

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Abstract

Purpose: The present study analyses the role of HRA competencies in determining the financial outcomes. Moreover, the study also examines the gap existing in the expected and existing competencies of HR analysts in Indian organizations. **Design/Methodology/Approach:** In the wake of findings from an in-depth literature review, the present study prepares a conceptual framework based on Capability Motivation and Opportunity (CMO) model to test the hypotheses on a sample size of 230 HR and HRA professionals which were formulated to analyse the relationship among the study variables. A quantitative methodology with a structured questionnaire was adopted to gather the data as it integrates the components of HRA competency and measures their impact on business outcomes. **Findings:** The findings demonstrated that business outcomes can be improved by providing motivation and opportunities to employees, who possess HR analytical skills. A Structural Equation Model was developed by the study to assess the compatibility of the proposed CMO framework in explaining the relationships among the study variables. **Practical Implications:** The application of data in the organizations has changed its mode and concentrated on fulfilling the legal wants of the employment. This change in the use of data gradually changed dynamics of Human Resource Management (HRM) role and the organizations expect good analysis quality from Human Resource (HR) professions. **Originality /Value:** The study provided a significant depiction of the role played by HRA in determining the business outcomes and the gap existing in the competencies exhibited by HR analysts, with respect to the competency levels expected from them. Still, not many researchers explored the role of HRA in increasing the business out come in the context of Indian organizations.

Keywords: HRM, HR Analytics, Decision-making, Financial productivity, CMO.

JEL codes: M1, M12, M5, M51, J81, J20, G32.

Introduction

One of the significant contributions of the present study is to examine the analytical aspects of human capital management in the organisational context and its importance in acquiring effective business solutions. Moreover, the study identifies the existing gaps between the expected and actual HRA competencies in Indian organisations. Also, the study endeavours to provide recommendations for academia and industry on the manner in which these gaps can be addressed. In addition, the study also throws light on how the capability, motivation and opportunities of the HR professionals can be utilised to increase the productivity and efficiency of the organisations. The need for companies to have an analytical reference point (HRA) for deriving constructive decisions that has a positive impact on the business results is also examined. Thus, it is expected that our study may contribute to theoretical inferences on the basis of the existing HR analytics parameters. It is also expected that the present study finds new prospective job criteria with good HR analytics practice. HR analysts can be designated as data analysts, data scientists, business analysts, big data analysts, market research analysts, financial analysts, etc. (Magnimind,2021). Three frameworks are commonly scrutinized when exploring the prospective use of HRA function in an organization. They are Business Analytics Success Pillars (BASP) framework, Capability-Opportunity-Motivation (COM) model, and Logical, Analytics, Measures, and Process (LAMP) framework. The present section reviews the studies pertaining to these frameworks of HRA.

Related Literature

The significant growth of access to HR technology, including human resource information systems (HRISs), cloud platforms and apps, has offered HR departments the ability to collect, manage and analyse large volumes of employee data, compared to earlier legacy IT systems (Bondarouk and Brewster, 2016; Marler and Boudreau, 2017; Kim *et al.*, 2021).

Acito and Khatri (2014) opined that the efficiency and effectiveness of a business is improved by the operation of data analytics. It is achieved by laying an impact in the operational fields like accounting, organizational or managerial networks such as supply chains and in commercial divisions, e.g. health management and wellness programs (Ward *et al.*, 2014). In the bandwagon of data analytics, HRM is a novice department, but the management recognizes its worth while acknowledging apprehension of their own institutional willingness for adoption.

The idea of making decisions based on several sources of information, including organizational facts such as analytics, is a foundational element in evidence-based practice (Walshe and Rundall, 2001; Briggs and McBeath, 2009; Rousseau and Barends, 2011; Baba and HakemZadeh, 2012; Coron, 2021)

It is popularly known by numerous terms, e.g. workforce/ talent/ HR or people analytics. The above-mentioned analytics have many things common in them. They are concerned with the analysis of data related to human resource departments, amalgamation of the data from different internal departments and even from the internal sources. Infotech departments help in accumulation, manipulation, interpretation and broadcasting of variety of data, which may be either structured or unstructured. All the analytics are utilised to reinforce decision-making, which is relevant to people in any organization and then associate HR decisions for better results in business and better performance of the employees in any organisation (Momin and Mishra, 2015).

During the 1940s, some of the big enterprises were utilising analytics to enhance and upgrade selection and talent management (Lawler, 2015). Nevertheless, with the onset of information technology, accumulation of the data and then the analysis followed by its interpretation has become much more convenient now. It has made workforce analytics easily attainable and employable practically for any organization. With few exclusions (Singh et al., 2012; Chadwick et al., 2020), many studies of the approximated "black box" of the HRM, performance relationship targets upon HR strategies instead of the execution of the HR department in formulating HR decisions.

Additionally, the data collected from various new sources such as wearable technology, email, and calendars render better favourable circumstances for understanding behaviours of the workers or employees and enhancing its performance which is not easy in the other case. This progression of analytical and evidence-based decision-making has tremendous promising opportunities for enhancing the effectiveness and productivity of the organisation. Regardless of ample propaganda and hype, there still lies a challenge with the organisation in terms of successful accomplishment and execution of workforce analytics. Many institutions endeavour strategic intuitiveness and awareness from their employee data by fabrication of workforce analytics teams and enforcements has delayed other tasks, which recurrently falls short of prediction (Ramussen and Ulrich, 2015). For instance, in a study which involved over 10,000 business and HR heads, Deloitte (2017) concluded that despite over 70% of those within the organisation believe that workforce analytics is a key factor to enhance performance of the employees and give a boost to the business, whereas, merely 8% of the firms reported having any form of useful data, while 9% opined that they know the type of talents in their workforce resulted in good performance, and 15% decided that three are talent indices or talent rosters for their managers.

Isson and Harriot (2013) adopted the BASP model to organize managers through different phases of analytical experience with the final objective of using business analytics to achieve a competitive edge. The seven pillars of BASP are: "business challenges, data foundation, analytics implementation, insight, execution and measurement, distributed knowledge, and innovation" (Figure 2.1). However, the authors exhibited scepticism regarding the capability of the model to address modern-day challenges.

BASP framework

Source: Isson and Harriot (2013)

An evidence-based method comprising of predictive modeling, HR metrics reporting, and an array of tools and technologies was adopted by Bassi (2011) for deciding on the people's aspect of business. A non-empirical

study was conducted, wherein individuals, groups, and companies were considered. The fact that whether organizational performance and outcome was affected by analytics was verified by using a variant of BASP model. It was found that organizational performance was not conclusively affected by HR analytics.

Baudreu and Ramstad (2006) examined the effect of analytics on organizational functioning. The researchers cited the example of Starbucks in evidencing the role of the COM model in yielding favourable outcomes. According to the authors, the COM model was used across 11,000 stores of Starbucks for comprehending and enhancing the performance. The study ascertained the role of COM model in the successful management of employees.

Levenson (2011) designed COM model to create test conditions to gain enhanced awareness of their employees' behaviour, performance, and motivation, to ask appropriate diagnostic queries, and to assist managers who cannot ask appropriate diagnostic queries or undertake comprehensive analytics. In this model, the time utilized on training and developing an employee in a new role to be fully productive was termed as capability. The official and unofficial practice that facilitate or obstruct the performance of employees was termed as opportunity. The model's motivation aspect signified factors like supervisors, peers, salary, etc., which may influence employees' motivation. The study demonstrated that the designed analytics model helped HR professionals to strategize, improve, and attain the desired business outcomes.

Research Methodology

In the wake of findings from an in-depth literature review, the present study prepares a conceptual framework based on Capability Motivation and Opportunity (CMO) model to test the hypotheses on a sample size of 230 HR and HRA professionals which were formulated to analyse the relationship among the study variables. A quantitative methodology with a structured questionnaire was adopted to gather the data as it integrates the components of HRA competency and measures their impact on business outcomes.

The framework provides the relationship between the variables adopted by the study. It integrates the existing and expected competency characteristics with four sub-variables each, namely, understanding of data, Analytical, and Interpretation skills and Capability, Motivation and Opportunity of the HR professionals with the utilisation of competency outcomes by the organisation for different processes on business outcomes of the various organisations where they are currently working. The measurement of Return on investments (ROI) and Decision making process formed the business outcomes of the organisations located in Bengaluru, Karnataka. The significance of the relationship between the variables was analysed using the hypotheses which are formulated with respect to the objectives of the study.

The objective of the present research is to understand the role of HRA competency of HRA professionals in the application on use of any competency outcomes obtained by the organisations, which in turn impacts the business outcomes.

The questionnaire of the study was subjected to reliability and validity analysis. This test was conducted to make sure that the constructs used in the study were accurate and fulfil the representation of the event to be tested.

Reliability Analysis

The current study used Cronbach's alpha (Cronbach, 1951) to analyse the internal consistency of the items used in the questionnaire, as advocated by Ritchie, Lewis and Elam (2003). The Cronbach's alpha values always lie between 0 and 1. However, values greater than 0.6 are considered as acceptable, while values

between 0.7 to 0.8 are considered satisfactory and more than 0.8 to less than 0.95 is considered to be good (Bland and Altman, 1997,ⁱ Hinton et al., 2014).

The reliability of the constructs used in the study was measured. According to the Table, most of the items on the scale, such as Understanding of data (4 items; $\alpha = 0.835$), Analytical skills (11 items; $\alpha = 0.828$) and Interpretation skills (5 items; $\alpha = 0.909$) within Existing HR analytical competencies; Analytical skills (11 items; $\alpha = 0.817$) and Interpretation skills (5 items; $\alpha = 0.841$) within the Expected HR analytical competencies, Process performance (10 items; $\alpha = 0.900$) and strategies (4 items; $\alpha = 0.803$) within Utilisation of the competency outcome by the organization for different processes; Knowledge (6 items; $\alpha = 0.928$), Skills (6 items; $\alpha = 0.950$) and Behaviour (5 items; $\alpha = 0.895$) within HRA capabilities; Cross functional dynamics (5 items; $\alpha = 0.887$) and Job design/ job responsibility (3 items; $\alpha = 0.901$) within the level of opportunities and Return on Investments (ROI) (7 items; $\alpha = 0.909$) and decision-making process (16 items; $\alpha = 0.938$) within business outcomes showed a good level of reliability. Understanding of data (4 items; $\alpha = 0.786$) within Expected HR analytical competencies and Organizational/Job fit (6 items; $\alpha = 0.763$) within the Level of motivation displayed a satisfactory level of reliability, while Creative analytics (5 items; $\alpha = 0.651$) within Level of motivation and Organizational infrastructure (3 items; $\alpha = 0.657$) showed acceptable levels of inter-item reliability ($\alpha > 0.6$). Thus, all the scales used in the study for measuring various constructs are reliable, which indicates that the results of the study are also reliable.

Validity Testing

The validity testing was conducted using exploratory factor analysis to ensure that the approach planned in the study was coordinated with the scales of measurement embraced by the researcher. The relevance of the data for factor analysis and the inter-correlations among the variables is analysed using Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO), which examines the sufficiency of samples (Kaiser, 1970) and Bartlett's test of Sphericity, which examines whether the sub-scales of the scale are inter-dependent by evaluating the significance of the correlation matrix (Williams, Vandenberg & Edwards, 2010). With the help of these factors, the researcher was able to determine the nature of variance between the factors for further factor analysis. The KMO values lie between 0 and 1; however, as an accepted convention, KMO values greater than 0.5 indicates adequate sampling, values ranging from 0.6 to 0.8 indicate moderate sampling and values above 0.9 are considered as excellent.

The Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) predicts whether the scales used in the questionnaire measure the phenomenon that is meant to be measured in an exact manner. EFA was adopted to categorize a large number of interrelated factors depending on their common factors. Thus, the primary purpose of carrying out the factor analysis is to reveal the hidden constructs that could explain the interrelationship between the measured constructs (Kahn, 2006). The EFA Eigenvalues represent the variance within the observed variables as explained by a particular construct. Eigenvalues greater than 1 were used as the base for deriving the factors (Henson & Roberts, 2006). Factors that loaded below 0.4 were suppressed for better reading of the results (Straub, Boudreau, and Gefen, 2004).

Result Presentation

The data obtained from HR analysts can be utilised for different processes such as performance processes and strategic processes in any organization. The most prominent role of HR analytics is to provide an intuitive approach about the manpower which can be considered for making better decisions. For an organization to excel in its performance, the contribution of each employee plays a major role. Based on the opinions

provided by the HR analysts, the organizations are utilising the data analysis competencies only up to a moderate extent as shown in Table. This was particularly followed in case of employee attitude surveys (3.739 ± 1.095), recruitment analysis (3.622 ± 1.322), management development assessments (3.709 ± 1.441) and design or dysfunctional aspects of workflow (3.478 ± 1.174). The data analysis was highly used for performance evaluations (4.026 ± 1.243) and, organisational development assessments (4.035 ± 1.129). However, performance processes such as compensation analysis (3.339 ± 1.278), downsizing workforce evaluation (3.022 ± 1.349) and labour compliance (3.339 ± 1.104) were being utilised only to some extent, implying a scope for improvement particularly in these areas. Overall, it can be inferred that the organizations were only focusing on applying data analysis outputs in assessing the overall performance of employees and organizational development. The application of data in assessing the individual operational and performance related factors is only moderate. This showcases the fact that the organizations were either not aware of the benefits of data analysis in enhancing the operations in a productive manner or facing challenges in appropriate data analysis

Existing HR Analytical Competencies

The KMO and Bartlett's test results for the factors considered for Existing HR analytical competencies is shown. The KMO value for existing HR analytical competencies was found to be 0.659, indicating moderate sampling strength and acceptability of the scale used for measuring Existing HR analytical competencies. The Bartlett's test of Sphericity testing the multivariate normality of the set of distributions and the strength of the relationship between the variables was found to be statistically significant with ($\chi^2 (253) = 5172.581$, $p < 0.05$). This shows the sampling adequacy of the participants of the study and the suitability of the data for performing factor analysis (Kaiser, 1970; Cerny and Kaiser, 1977).

Factor analysis performed on Existing HR analytic competencies yielded three factors, understanding of data, analytical skills and interpretation skills as given in Table. The survey responses were used for extracting these factors with the help of the principal component extraction method along with varimax rotation and Kaiser Normalization. Understanding of data was the most important factor and explained about 28.341% of the total variation in the existing HR analytic competencies. This was followed by analytical skills which explained 16.8% variable, followed by interpretation skills which covers 15.898% of the total variation in the variance. The entire factor, Existing HR analytical competencies explained 61.04% of the variability in the data. From the results, it can be inferred that as an existing HRA professional, understanding of data is the most important competency required by the HR analysts. Further, the results also show that analysis and interpretation of the data carry almost equal weight-age, indicating that both these skills are equally necessary for obtaining meaningful inferences.

Expected HR Analytic Competencies

The results of KMO and Bartlett's sphericity test pertaining to expected HR analytic competencies. The KMO value was found to be 0.629, indicating moderate sampling, while the Bartlett's test of Sphericity was found to be statistically significant ($p < 0.05$) with χ^2 value of 4326.674 and $p < 0.05$ at 300 degrees of freedom. This result implies that the data is approximately multivariate normal and acceptable for factor analysis.

Competency Outcomes using Strategic Processes

The strategic processes used by the HR analysts involves developing a strategic model for the overall development of the organization. The overall average of 3.669 ± 1.287 implies that this process has also not been utilised to a great extent, but only to a moderate extent as shown in Table. In fact, all the tested

parameters such as employee promotion strategies (3.626 ± 1.152), HR manpower planning (4.009 ± 1.118) and change in management planning (3.626 ± 1.278) are utilised up to a moderate extent, whereas, succession planning for leadership development (3.417 ± 1.200) was utilised lesser complying only to some extent. Thus, an inference can be made that the HR professionals were good at utilising the competency outcomes in strategic processes to a moderate extent.

Business outcomes and HRA

Business outcome was measured by evaluating the return on investments (ROI) and the level of the decision-making process of HR analysts towards human resources analytics in the organizations. In the recent years, there has been an increased tendency in many organizations towards data-driven decision formulations in discrete form of business (Holsapple, 2014). This can be achieved using big data in day to day activities (Chong and Shi, 2015). Today's HR transformation is a straightforward development of swift advancement within organizations caused due to the united forces of demographics, globalization and information technology.

Return on Investments (ROI) and HRA

ROI-based business outcomes enable organizational vision and helps in enhancing organizational performance. The perceptions of the HR professionals towards ROI are shown in Table. It can be seen that the HR professionals are highly agreeable with the fact that the analysts will improve the efficiency of business process (4.083 ± 0.746) and learning curve of the organization (4.048 ± 0.761). The HR professionals also concurred that there are wide applications of analytics that will change the organization's results drastically (3.900 ± 0.986). In addition, the respondents also agreed that that HR analytics helped in enhancing the business efficiency of the operating standards and measuring the impact of employee and performance of the organization (3.839 ± 0.928) to 3.913 ± 0.877). The HR analysts also helped to link each activity to the business bottom-line very objectively (3.800 ± 0.811). Thus, the findings suggested that there was a return on investment due to HR analysts in the organizations.

Decision-Making Process and HR Analysts

The decision-making process forms a crucial part in obtaining business outcomes using HR Analytics. As shown in Table, the HR professionals agreed that analytics cut the unnecessary opinion based decision-making in the organizations (3.687 ± 0.797). There was a routine measurement of HR activities in terms of payroll, benefits and other forms of communications (3.978 ± 0.708). The effectiveness of HR practices was evaluated prior to implementation (3.996 ± 0.733). Moreover, the expenses behind providing HR services (3.822 ± 0.861), performance of outsourced activities (3.957 ± 0.652) and practicality behind new ideas (3.974 ± 0.705) were assessed. Decisions were taken to show the competitive status (3.926 ± 0.984) and business plans with the management of human capital (3.983 ± 0.620) of the organizations. The effectiveness of HR programs on workforce (3.996 ± 0.630) and business outcomes (3.843 ± 0.863) was also evaluated. In addition, it was understood that the human capital practices were linked to organizational performance (3.922 ± 0.858) and any not so useful HR program was discontinued (3.843 ± 0.607). All the processes that involved decision-making were conducted by the HR analysts. Thus, it can be inferred that the HR professionals agreed with that decision-making process forms an integral part of business outcomes.

Utilisation of Competency Outcome

The KMO and Bartlett's Test of Sphericity was performed to analyse the utilisation of competency outcome by the organization for different processes (Table). The KMO value was found to be 0.7340, indicating moderate sampling, while the Bartlett's test of Sphericity was found to be statistically significant ($p < 0.05$)

with χ^2 value of 2335.882 and $p < 0.05$ at 66 degrees of freedom. This result suggests that the data is approximately multivariate normal and acceptable for factor analysis.

KMO and Bartlett's Test for Utilisation of Competency Outcome by the Organization for Different Processes

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy		0.734
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	2335.822
	Df	66
	Sig.	0.000

According to the factor analysis, the utilisation of the competency outcomes of the organizations for different processes revealed two main sub-factors: process performance and strategies. Process performance was revealed to be the most significant factor, which accounted for 48.555% of the total variation, while strategies contributed towards 23.261% of the total variance in the data. As a whole, utilisation of competency outcome by the organization for different processes was responsible for 71.816% of the total variability in the data.

Factors of Utilisation of Competency Outcome by the Organization for Different Processes

Factors	Factor Loadings	% of Variance	Cumulative %
Process Performance		48.555	48.555
Downsizing workforce assessment	0.840		
Organization design/dysfunctional aspects of work flow	0.834		
Organizational development assessments	0.812		
Employee attitude surveys	0.796		
Compensation analysis	0.780		
Recruitment analysis	0.741		
Employee competency assessments	0.766		
Employee performance assessments	0.707		
Management development assessments	0.609		
Strategies		23.261	71.816
HR manpower planning	0.840		
Succession planning for leadership development	0.818		
Change management planning	0.638		

HRA Capability

The KMO and Bartlett's Test of Sphericity was performed to analyse the capabilities of the HR analysts. The KMO value for HR capabilities was found to be 0.833, indicating excellent sampling. The Bartlett's test of Sphericity between the variable was statistically significant with χ^2 value of 3497.057 and $p < 0.05$ at 105 degrees of freedom. This shows the suitability of responses obtained from the questionnaire and the validity of performing factor analysis on the data.

KMO and Bartlett's Test for HRA Capability

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy		0.833
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	3497.057
	Df	105
	Sig.	0.000

Using factor analysis, it was revealed the HRA capabilities explained 81.396% variance in the data. The HRA capability showed that there are three factors in HRA capabilities, namely, knowledge, skills and behaviour. Within HRA capabilities, Knowledge was the most vital factor and explained for 35.303% of the total variation in the HRA capability. This was followed by Skills, which explained 29.187% and behaviour which contributed to 16.905% of total variation in the variable. Moreover, the entire factor under each item had a factor loading value greater than 0.4, confirming that all those factors played a significant part in measuring the HRA capability.

Factors of HRA Capability

Factors	Factor Loadings	% of Variance	Cumulative %
Knowledge		35.303	35.303
Knowledge of organizational design factors	0.873		
Knowledge of cost management	0.851		
Knowledge of employee retention tactics	0.802		
Knowledge of the external market and customer demands	0.685		
Knowledge on how to assess the job design	0.639		
Knowledge of the company's culture and relationships with former employees	0.552		
Skills		29.187	64.491
Skills for analysing internal and external environments (e.g., understand vendor requirements, etc).	0.843		
Skills of change management	0.830		
Skills to understand the causal factors of outcome	0.741		
Skills for identifying the content of the analysis	0.683		
Skills to transfer training into practice on the floor.	0.682		
Behaviour		16.905	81.396
We meet the timeline of the given task consistently	0.850		
We have the ability to transfer the training into actual practice	0.731		
We diligently perform the given task to meet the quality standards	0.728		
We share the analytical knowledge to fellow employee in a quick and an unproblematic way	0.692		

Level of Opportunities

The KMO value for level of opportunities was found to be 0.806, which denotes excellent sampling. The Bartlett's test of Sphericity was observed to be statistically significant ($\chi^2(55) = 1878.417, p < 0.05$). This suggests the responses were suitable for performing factor analysis of the data.

KMO and Bartlett's Test for Level of Opportunities

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		0.806
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	1878.417
	Df	55
	Sig.	0.000

The exploratory factor analysis on level of opportunities showed that it explained 79.605% variance in the data and three factors, namely, organizational infrastructure, cross functional dynamics and job design were revealed. Among them, the organizational infrastructure was the most prominent factor and explained

40.848% of the total variation in the HRA capability. This was followed by cross functional dynamics which explained 23.283% of the total variation and job design which contributed to 15.474% of total variation in the variable.

Factors of Level of Opportunities

Factors	Factor Loadings	% of Variance	Cumulative %
Organizational infrastructure		40.848	40.848
Platform to use analytics in every aspect of the job	0.924		
Infrastructure facilities to perform the tasks	0.908		
Access the right data	0.756		
Cross-functional dynamics		23.283	64.131
Platform to develop plans for improving managerial performance	0.888		
Platforms for cross-training	0.846		
Opportunity to develop my leadership skills	0.731		
Opportunity to perform cross-functional roles	0.696		
Platforms for communicating and engaging employees	0.662		
Job design		15.474	79.605
Opportunities to use my analytical skills	0.746		
Opportunities to discuss about analytics with my team members	0.703		
Opportunity to be aware of various statistical tools from team members	0.611		

Level of Motivation

A similar analysis carried out for level of motivation showed that the KMO value was 0.611, which implies moderate sampling, appropriate for the study. The Bartlett's Test of Sphericity was found to be significant (p=0.000) at the 0.05 level of significance with $\chi^2 = 1937.313$ with 91 degrees of freedom, suggesting the suitability of the data for factor analysis.

KMO and Bartlett's Test for Level of Motivation

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy		0.611
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	1937.313
	Df	91
	Sig.	0.000

As per factor analysis, the level of motivation revealed three factors: organizational fit, creative analysis and job satisfaction. It is evident that the level of motivation factor together accounted for 67.797% of the total variance, with organizational fit contributing to 26.840% and creative analytics contributing to 22.560% individually, respectively. Job satisfaction explained about 18.397% of the total variation in the level of motivation. Thus, the findings indicate that the most important motivating factor is to determine whether the HR professional is fit for the organization, followed by their creative analytical skills and level of job satisfaction

Factors of Level of Motivation

Factors	Factor Loadings	% of Variance	Cumulative %
Organizational fit		26.840	26.840
Developing metrics and measures to assess the employees is most pivot in my job	0.875		
My job demands experimentation and generating new product ideas	0.801		
My job demands customizing the way of delivery of our services	0.778		
My job demands more technology oriented tasks	0.770		
There is supervisor's and peer encouragement in my job	0.761		
My job demands self-managed teams	0.678		
Creative analytics		22.560	49.400
My job demands finding new recruitment channels	0.789		
There is a performance-based assessment of employees	0.756		
There are a lot of incentives to use creative analytics in my process	0.670		
There is a challenging work-environment in my job	0.600		
Job Satisfaction		18.397	67.797
There is work-life balance in my job	0.865		
There are incentive compensation and reward system in my job	0.854		
There is good pay and benefit system in my job	0.676		
There is satisfaction in my job	0.616		

Business Outcome

The results of KMO test and Bartlett's test of sphericity conducted for business outcomes. The KMO value was found to be 0.683, indicative of moderate sampling. The Bartlett's Test of Sphericity was observed to be significant ($p=0.000$) at the 0.05 level of significance with $\chi^2(171) = 4320.184$, suggesting the suitability of the data for factor analysis.

KMO and Bartlett's Test for Business Outcomes

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy		0.683
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	4320.184
	Df	171
	Sig.	0.000

The factor analysis of Business outcomes showed that it explained 65.808% variation in the data and revealed two factors, namely, Return on Investment (ROI) and decision-making as presented. Among those, ROI explained about 36.623% of the total variation, followed by decision-making which explained 29.185% of total variation in the variable. Moreover, the entire factor under each item had a factor loading value greater than 0.4, confirming that all those factors played a significant part in measuring the business outcome. Thus, it can be implied that ROI plays a bigger role, followed by decision-making process in obtaining business outcomes by the HR professionals.

Factors of Business Outcome

Factors	Factor Loadings	% of Variance	Cumulative %
Return on Investments (ROI)		36.623	36.623
Wide application of analytics will change the organization results drastically.	0.912		
Analytics helps to link each activity to the business bottom-line very objectively.	0.821		
Analytics will enhance the efficiency of the business process.	0.769		
The learning curve of the organization is enhanced.	0.749		
Analytics helps to evaluate the efficiency of the operating standards.	0.748		
The company in the position to assess the ROI on training.	0.580		
Decision-making process		29.185	65.808
Point out HR programs that should be discontinued.	0.852		
Link human capital practices to organizational performance.	0.851		
Measure the cost of providing HR services.	0.811		
Outcome of key HR activities like man power planning can be forecasted well.	0.771		
Identify the area where talent has the maximum scope for strategic impact.	0.770		
Measure routine HR activities (payroll, benefits, communication, etc.).	0.765		
Evaluate and track the performance of outsourced HR activities	0.732		
Getting input from analytics process key input for business decisions, especially from strategic perspectives.	0.728		
Contribute to decisions about business plans and human capital management.	0.698		
Analytics cuts the unnecessary opinion based decision-making in the organization.	0.682		
Make decisions that reflect your company's competitive status.	0.681		
Evaluate and improve the human capital strategy of the company.	0.669		
Evaluate the practicality of new business strategies.	0.613		

Conclusion

Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) was carried out in this study as an additional mechanism to assess the validity of the scales. It is considered as a rigorous way of testing the construct validity of a questionnaire over other traditional ways of testing (Medsker, Williams & Holahan, 1994). The uni-dimensionality of the measurement scales established by EFA were reconfirmed by the factor loadings obtained by CFA. It is known that CFA does not require any additional information for verifying the validity of the scales, hence it was considered for this study. Further, CFA is usually adopted when the study constructs are measured using a set of items and the items have a linear relationship with the average of the scales (Levine, 2005). The scales used in the study meet both of these two criteria, therefore, CFA was adopted for establishing the validity of the scales. The results of CFA helped the researcher to determine the items that were measured by particular constructs and the difference in constructs. This established the validity of the scales for measuring the constructs.

Policy Implications

The scales measuring Existing HRA competency as well as Expected HRA competency, Utilisation of HRA competencies, HRA capability, Opportunities, Level of motivation and Business outcomes were subjected to CFA. CFA was carried out by first specifying a measurement model. The goodness-of-fit of the model, i.e. how well the data fits the hypothetical structure, was determined using a set of indices suggested by Kline (2011) and Bagozzi and Yi (2012). The goodness-of-fit indices considered by the researcher included the chi-

square statistics and other measures of close fit, including Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA), comparative fit index (CFI), and Tucker-Lewis Index (TLI). The RMSEA refers to the “discrepancy between the estimated and observed covariance matrices per degree of freedom in terms of the population, not the sample” (Hair et al., 2010), whereas, the CFI compares the estimated model with the null model and is sensitive to the sample size of the study (Kline, 2011). TLI, on the other hand, “compares the estimated model fit to a null model, and takes into account the model parsimony by assessing the degrees of freedom from the estimated model to the degrees of freedom of the null model” (Garver & Mentzer, 1999). It does not depend on the sample size. The accepted threshold values for RMSEA is between 0.5 and 0.8 while the recommended values for CFI and TLI is 0.90. After determining the overall fit of the model, the uni-dimensionality of the measurement model was tested by assessing the standardized factor loadings and t-values. The composite reliability estimates were used to determine the reliability of the model and its validity was tested through convergent and divergent validity. The validated model was used for constructing the overall structural model and test the hypothesized relationships.

Future Research

The present study covers only a small representation of the population of HR professionals. In addition, it focuses on HR professionals from the city of Bengaluru, Karnataka. The same conclusion needs to be drawn from the rest of the country. Future studies can expand the research to include the whole of India with a greater number of respondents. Further, the study only focuses on the impact of HRA on business outcome, it did not explore the factors that influence the HR analytics competence. This can be explored in the future studies.

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